

A STUDY ON CHALLENGING FACED BY OF WOMEN AGRICULTURAL FORMERS IN PALAYAMKOTTAI TALUK

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Abstract

Agriculture is one of the major segment playing a essential role in the country's economy. Specially in agriculture most of women laborers contributing their work for the development of agriculture but still in our country the women agricultural formers condition is very poor, low wages paid, some unpaid works and asset lessness. In this background, this study the paper was conducted on economic conditions of women agricultural formers in Palayamkottai Taluk. The data collected from 200 women agricultural formers with the help of well-prepared interview schedule. Further the study analyse the economic position, working conditions and employment status. The researcher has applied factor analysis, percentage analysis and Garrett ranking to get the most accurate result for interpretation.

Keywords: *Agriculture, Borrowings, Economic conditions, Women formers .*

Introduction

Women are the backbone of the progress of rural and national economies. Agriculture is main selection for rural women to be away from housekeeping activities. Their work was considered as “help” but their hard work not be considered as well as their work not consider as productive and economic activities. Women need money to fulfill their needs as well as run their day to day family life. Women have more self respect they never want to show that they are loser, they are willing to earn money and they have a loan of some amount from bank as well as money lenders and sometimes from their friends.

Agriculture Economy in India

India's economy mostly depends on agriculture. In our country, a total of 70% of the population is in rural areas from that 60% of the households are involved in agriculture. Most of the poor people work in agriculture all the time. Women are the main producer of food grains and always they are engaged in agriculture-related activities. Nearby 70% of the farm-related activities are done by women.

Table 1, Economic Status of Women Formers

Annual Agricultural Income	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Less than 30,000	58	29	29
30,000-50000	97	48.5	77.5
Above 50000	45	22.5	100
Total	200	100.0	
Mode of wage payment			
Time wages	79	39.5	39.5
Contract wags	121	60.5	100.0
Total	200	100.0	
Wage distribution			
Daily	104	52	52

Weekly	96	48	100.0
Total	200	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

While observing the economic status of the women formers most of the respondents earned between 30000 – 50000 per annum that is (97) 48.5 percent, more than (121) 60.5 percent of the respondents are getting their wages on a contract basis and (104) 52 percent of the respondents are receiving their wages daily. Hence it is inferred that most of the respondents are earning 30000 to 50000 per annum and they are working on a daily wage contract basis.

Banking Process of Women Agriculture Formers

Most of the women farmers are having savings account in the bank and they are ready to get loan from bank but they facing some sort of difficulties faced by getting loans

Table 2, Loan and Banking process

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Borrowings			
Yes	177	88.5	88.5
No	33	11.5	100.0
Total	200	100.0	
Purpose of loan			
Fertilizer	16	9.0	9.0
Farm equipments	17	9.6	18.6
Daughter's marriage	14	7.9	26.5
repay to money lender	30	16.9	43.4
For business	14	7.9	51.3
repay bank's old debt	16	9.0	62.3
Medical treatment	18	10.1	72.4
Purchase household assets	16	9.0	81.4
Cultivation and farming	22	12.4	93.8
Purchase cattles	14	7.9	100.0
Total	177	100.0	
Documents opted for loan			
Adangal	20	11.2	11.2
Jewels	157	88.8	100
Total	177	100	
Loan or interest subsidy			
Yes	128	72.3	72.3
No	49	27.7	100
Total	177	100	
Mode of repayment			
Monthly	32	18.1	18.1
Quarterly	26	14.7	32.8
Half Yearly	54	30.5	63.3

Yearly	65	36.7	100
Total	177	100	
Rate of Interest for loan (%)			
5	44	24.8	24.8
7	50	28.2	53
8	62	35	88
Above 10	21	12	100
Total	177	100	

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, Out of 200 respondents, (177) 88.5 percent of the respondents have taken a bank loan and they utilized the amount for various purposes not only for agriculture in that most of the respondents (30) 16.9 percent used it to repay the debts for money lenders followed that cultivation and farming (22) 12.4 and (157) 88.8 percent of the respondents got the loan by pledging Jewels and remaining (60)10 percent of the respondents are used adangal document, and (128) 72.3 percent of the respondents benefitted from the government loan or interest subsidy, they have many options to repay the loan but most of the respondents (65) 36.7 percent are repaid their debts in annual basis, while most of the respondents are pledging their jewels due to that (62) 35 percent of the respondents are paying 8% interest per annum.

Table 3, Garrett ranking analysis for Problems in availing loan

Problems	Total	Mean Score	Rank
Bank official's partiality	33586	55.96	1
Insufficient repayment period of loan	32404	54.00	2
Rate of interest is High	31025	51.71	3
Lack of transparency	30967	51.61	4
Rate of interest is High More paper work	29398	48.98	5
Complicated loan procedure	29229	48.71	6
Value of security is high	28882	48.13	7
Bribe	28481	47.47	8
Delay in loan sanctioning	28248	47.06	9
High level formalities	27178	45.28	10

Source: Derived

The above table clearly shows the Garrett ranking for problems in availing of loan, Bank official's partiality while allotting the loan ranks first with a mean score of 55.96 which is followed by insufficient repayment period of loan, high rate of interest, lack of transparency, rigid loan procedure, more paper work, bribe, high value of security, delay in loan sanctioning and high-level formalities gets the final rank. Therefore, women need extra time to repay the money and transparency in allotting the loan.

Table 4 ,Rotated Factor Analysis for the Problems in availing loan

Rotated Component Matrix			
	Components		
	1	2	3
Delay in loan process	.928	-.018	-.161
Rate of interest high	.903	.156	.018
Complicated loan procedure	.687	.547	.099
Bribe	-.765	-.219	-.369
Value of security is high	.050	.697	-.085
Bank official's partiality	.049	.681	.472
High level formalities	-.539	-.666	.192
More paper work	-.523	-.008	.595
Lack of transparency	-.118	-.478	.734
Insufficient repayment period of loan	-.294	-.183	-.814
Variance	34.034	20.271	19.949
Cumulative %	34.034	54.305	74.254
Total %	45.83	27.3	26.87
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.			

Borrowing Constraint

Rigid Loan Procedures, Delay in sanctioning loans, rate of interest is high and Bribe is the most important problem faced by women while applying for a loan. This factor has a variance of 34.034 percent and forms 45.83 percent of total

Procedural Constraint

Banks are availing of loans by pledging jewels or based on the security documents submitted to them, so the following variables are categorized in this constraint they are, high value of security, bank officials partiality, and more formalities. This factor has a variance of 20.271 percent and forms 27.3 percent of the total.

Transparency Constraint

Every agricultural woman formers receive a salary daily basis so that they cannot able to save for later but in banks, they are availing minimum 6 months to 1 year to repay the loan but it is not enough for the women workers. In this category following variables are categorized, insufficient repayment period of the loan, lack of transparency, and more paperwork. This factor has a variance of 19.95 percent and forms 26.87 percent of the total.

Table 5 ,Component Transformation Matrix for the Problems in Availing loan

Components	Sanction of loan	Procedure	Transparency
Sanction of loan	.864	.503	.005
Procedure	-.057	.087	.995
Transparency	-.500	.860	-.104
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.			

Source: Derived

Conclusion

Women contribute more than man formers in agriculture and its co-related activities. She is doing the work from the cultivated area till harvesting but they are low paid compared to men and they have to work more hours than committed and the income the agriculture is not enough to fulfill all her needs. They have a lot of complicated while applying for the loan and getting the loan is a very big process and has more troubles for agricultural women, rigid loan procedures, partiality in sanction of amount, delay in sanction, and not enough repayment periods are the most common challenge faced by women agricultural formers. Thus, the government should take steps to overcome these burdens.

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